

EUROPEAN INVESTMENT PROGRAMS IN THE ECONOMY OF UKRAINE: HORIZON EUROPE PROGRAM

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The European Union (EU) and individual European countries have been actively supporting Ukraine's economy, especially since the start of the war in 2022. Investment programs are aimed at restoration, infrastructure modernization, development of small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs), as well as green energy and digital transformation.

The main European investment programs at this time include the following:

- Horizon Europe program: aims to support research and technological development, including innovative start-ups. Ukraine received associate membership, which allows access to grants and partnerships;
- European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD): invests in infrastructure projects, energy, the agricultural sector, as well as in financing small businesses. Important areas: support for women entrepreneurs and sustainable development projects;
- EU4Business initiative: provides support to Ukrainian small and medium-sized businesses through grants, loans, training programmes and consultations;
- InvestEU program: aimed at mobilizing private capital for large infrastructure projects and restoring key sectors of the economy.

The Horizon Europe program is a key European program for funding research, innovation and technological development. Its budget for the period 2021-2027 is more than €95.5 billion, making it the largest investment program for science and innovation in the history of the EU. Ukraine received the status of an associate member of the Horizon Europe program in 2022, which provides equal access to its opportunities on an equal basis with EU member states.

The main directions of the Horizon Europe program are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Areas and programs of funding from the Horizon Europe fund

Direction of financing	Funding programs
Green Transition	Financing energy innovations, including renewables, energy efficiency and carbon footprint reduction.
	Support for projects that contribute to the achievement of EU climate goals (e.g. European Green Deal).
Ohorona zdorov'ya	Research in the field of biotechnology, new vaccines, medical technologies
	Programs to combat pandemics and support biomedical research
Digitalization and technologies of the future	Investments in the development of digital tools, artificial intelligence, blockchain technologies, quantum computing
	Support for startups that create innovative products
Support for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs)	Special grants for startups and innovative SMEs
	EIC Accelerator Program — financing projects with high potential for market implementation

Source: author's development

The European Commission has announced the allocation of funding under the Horizon Europe research and innovation program for 2023-2024 in the amount of €13.5 billion, which provides for the search for advanced technologies for the further technological and economic development of the EU, as well as measures to support Ukraine.

Forms and methods of financial assistance to the Ukrainian economy by the Horizon Europe program are presented in Table 2.

In our opinion, the most important and relevant areas of using the financial opportunities of the Horizon Europe program for the Ukrainian economy can be the following:

- renewable energy projects for sustainable development of regions;
- research in the field of climate change and ecology;

- innovative IT solutions for public administration.

Table 2

Background and Funding Objects from the Horizon Europe Programme

Prerequisites for financing	Objects of financing
Access to finance	Ukrainian research institutions, universities, businesses, and non-governmental organizations can apply for grants
	Priority is given to projects in the field of innovation of European value
Expanding cooperation with the EU	Horizon Europe contributes to the integration of Ukrainian science into the European Research Area
	Ukrainian projects can participate in joint consortia with European partners
Restoration and modernization	Horizon Europe supports the development of technologies for the restoration of Ukraine's infrastructure, especially in the post-war period

Source: author's development

The Horizon Europe program is a unique opportunity for Ukrainian enterprises, researchers and startups to integrate into European economic and scientific processes. This program is an important resource for stimulating economic development and integration of Ukraine into the European economy. targeted assistance for Ukraine will be provided in addition to measures that provide funding of €70 million and have already been launched in 2022. The new measures will ensure access to the European Research Infrastructure for Ukrainian scientists, continue targeted support for Ukrainian scientists in the field of medicine, as well as conduct climate-neutral reconstruction of several Ukrainian cities using the capabilities of the so-called EU Mission for Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities. To participate in the program, businesses and organizations must meet the established criteria, as well as actively cooperate with local and international partners.